

ARCHITECTURAL RESILIENCE: NAVIGATING CLIMATIC CHALLENGES IN SECONDARY SCHOOL BUILDINGS ACROSS PORT HARCOURT LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, RIVERS STATE

Annotation:

In the Port Harcourt Local Government Area (LGA) of Rivers State, this study set out to determine how weather affects secondary school enrollment and occupancy rates. In particular, the study aimed to determine how factors like temperature, wind speed and direction, and sun radiation affect the use of secondary school buildings in Port Harcourt Local Government Area, Rivers State. With a focus on Port Harcourt, this study used a survey research technique. The research included all licenced general contractors and teachers working in the Port Harcourt LGA. In the Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State, a grand total of 180 people participated; 80 of those people were builders, and 100 were educators. Statistical analysis was based on a census sampling strategy. In this study, the researchers used a questionnaire to collect data. The poll measures "Building Technology Climatic Elements" (BTCEQ), as the name implies. Very high extent (VHE), high extent (HE), uncertain (U), low extent (LE), and very low extent (VLEA) were the five-point response possibilities that formed the instrument. Each choice had a value of 5, 4, 3, 2, or 1. The tool has been face-validated by three professionals and has a reliability coefficient of 0.68. Findings showed that residents of the Port Harcourt LGA in Rivers State agreed that temperature significantly affected the use of secondary school facilities. A large majority of people surveyed in the Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State agreed that wind significantly affected the occupancy rates of secondary school buildings, according to the study's findings. The study's results informed the following suggestions: In order to ensure that schools can adapt to different climates during construction, the ministry of education should lay down basic requirements. The use of sustainable building practices, construction methods and materials for the construction of secondary school buildings and educational facilities should be enshrined in the requirement for statutory approvals from regulatory bodies.

Keywords:

Climatic Elements, Secondary School Buildings.

Information about the authors

DIMKPA, Kelechukwu, PhD.
OHOCHUKU, P. Chinwennwo, PhD.
ADIBE, OKWAKPAM Nkeiruka.
OKEY-EJIOWHOR, Happiness Caleb.

*Department of Architecture,
Faculty of Environmental Sciences, Rivers State University, Nigeria*

Introduction

The physical location of a school is an integral part of the dynamic process that takes place there while students study. Proper instruction and learning can only take place in structures that are both functional

and valuable, not simply any old buildings. Public and private schools in Delta State both have their share of management and maintenance issues, as is evident from a quick inspection of the state's educational facilities today. The terrible condition of the state's educational facilities is the result of several causes. Geographical considerations, not maintenance personnel numbers, training, or management methods, are the root of most building issues in schools, according to Ajibade (2019). The location's climate and geography significantly affect the structure.

When designing a building, it's crucial to think about how the weather may affect the final product. There is a strong correlation between the climate and the building's orientation, location, and the materials employed. An optimally designed building may minimise energy consumption and other expensive maintenance needs while simultaneously increasing sustainability, safety, and efficiency.

The local temperature, humidity, precipitation, wind speed and direction, and sun radiation are all factors that must be considered while analysing climate. All of these things have the potential to significantly affect the building's design and the materials utilised to create it. For instance, compared to timber and other organic materials, concrete and other masonry materials are better at keeping humidity from penetrating structures in warm and humid climates. However, organic materials like wood, which are very insulating, will be more suited for use in cold climates since they assist to keep heat within the house. Similarly, in hot climates, building orientation is crucial, as facing east or west can reduce the likelihood of direct sunlight reaching the structure, hence lowering the cooling requirements.

The building materials also reveal the significance of climate. Because of their increased thermal insulation value, warm-climate building materials like brick, tile, and stone are preferable. When it's cold outside, it's best to use insulating materials like clay, straw, or wood. In addition, the local weather has an effect on the level of insulation. Insulating materials, like radiant barriers or foam insulation, are a good choice in colder climates (Akinniyi, 2016). You should choose for less insulating materials that can nevertheless support Elements such as temperature, wind speed and direction, sunshine intensity, humidity, and the frequency and amount of precipitation.

The primary element that dictates the air temperature is the rate of surface heating and cooling. Because the air is completely permeable to the sun's rays, their impact on air temperature is marginal at best. Convection, turbulence, and eddy currents carry the heat from the air layer that is closest to the warm ground to higher layers of the atmosphere (Arens, 2016). As a result of these eddy currents and winds, huge swaths of air are heated as they come into touch with the Earth's surface. In winter, the earth's surface is typically cool at night due to long wave radiation reaching the sky, which causes the reversal of heat exchange and cools the air that comes into contact with the ground. When exposed to the same amount of sunlight, water surfaces are less affected than land surfaces. That is why, at the same attitude, land is hotter and colder than sea in summer and winter, respectively. A shift in elevation also has an effect on the weather. As the air rises, its pressure drops, causing it to cool down, and the opposite is also true. The variation is 1 degree Celsius for every hundred metres. The evolution of latent heat occurs throughout the condensation process, which inhibits cooling as long as the process of water vapour condensing to droplets continues. This decrease is defined by the lapse rate. The lapse rate fluctuates during the day and according to the season, but it typically measures 0.6°C every 100 metres. Since the air layer close to the ground is warmer, the lapse rate is higher during the daytime. The lower air layer becomes unstable and continually mixes with the higher layer as a result of the hot air expanding and rising. The air closer to the ground cools down faster than the air further above because the earth's surface cools down more quickly than air throughout the night. In the vicinity of the ground, this causes the typical vertical temperature gradient to reverse. Surface inversion describes this occurrence. There is less vertical air movement and more stability since the bottom air layer is heavy and chilly (Bessoudo, et al., 2010). Long nights, bright skies, dry air, and no breeze make these circumstances dominate. Valleys and other low-lying places get a disproportionate share of the cold air near the ground, which may result in much lower temperatures than higher terrain.

The direction of the wind is the angle at which it is moving. In order to properly conduct aerodynamic building construction in the event of strong winds, it is crucial to have knowledge about the direction of the wind in each place, specifically the direction from which the wind blows more often (prevailing wind). It was common practice in ancient times to align the length of wind ward vents with the direction of the prevailing wind in tropical places like Yazd and Kerman. This allowed for the most efficient use of wind to cool buildings. Additionally, wind speed is significant because, particularly for lighter construction components, high-speed winds pose a threat of separation and physical damage. A key component of wind power mitigation is familiarity with the project site's average wind speed as well as its seasonal and yearly dispersion. The strength of the structure should be proportional to the local mean wind speed. When faced with many geographical options for a project, it's wise to choose the one with the lowest wind speed (Chan, et al., 2014). Wind pattern planning and wind speed monitoring at several locations in an area establish these zones. Building in an area with a lot of high-speed wind is a must if harnessing wind energy is to be a priority, such as when constructing wind power plants. The scenario clearly involves an upward wind that is steady and strong for much of the year, if not all of it.

The vertical stability of the air has a significant impact on the adiabatic cooling of huge air masses, which in turn causes precipitation and the development of clouds on a wide scale. As air pressure rises, it expands and cools until it reaches its dew point. Clouds made of millions of microscopic water droplets and, sometimes, frozen crystals develop as a result of large-scale condensation. Precipitation starts when enough heavy droplets fall and withstand the evaporative loss that occurs during their descent (Chand, 2016). Good, pleasant, and healthy living conditions are the ultimate goal of planning and design. A well-planned structure strikes a balance between the many factors that influence its appearance, such as the arrangement of its individual parts, the materials used in its construction, its physical layout, its landscaping, its orientation in relation to the sun and the wind, and so on.

Humidity in the atmosphere is the concentration of water vapour in the air. Most of the water vapour in the air comes from the oceans because of evaporation. The wind spreads the vapour all over the world. As the temperature rises, the air's ability to hold water vapour increases, leading to a distribution of vapour that is not uniform over the planet. It peaks in the middle of the ocean and gradually decreases as one moves closer to the poles (Cowan, et al., 2014).

Quantity of water vapour in grammes per cubic metre of air. Vapour density, measured in grammes per cubic metre Air. Pressure of vapour The part of the total atmospheric pressure that is associated with water vapour is measured in millimetres of mercury. To find the relative humidity at any given temperature, take the actual absolute humidity (AUH) and divide it by the maximum moisture capacity (MCC) of the air at that temperature. For example, if the air's absolute humidity is 8 g/m³ and saturated air at that same temperature contains 10 g/m³, the ratio is 8:10. When expressed as a percentage, the RH would be $8 \times 100 / 10 = 80\%$. At 100% relative humidity, the air has absorbed all the water vapour it can hold. This state is known as saturation. Because the rate of perspiration is directly proportional to the vapour pressure difference between the skin's surface and the air around it, measuring the air's vapour pressure is the most physiologically sound way to convey the current humidity levels. How various buildings respond and how quickly they deteriorate are both affected by the RH. While humidity has no direct effect on the amount of heat that the body experiences, it does regulate the air's evaporative capacity and, by extension, the effectiveness of perspiration in cooling down the body.

The unit of measurement for this electromagnetic radiation is microns, which is equal to one thousandth of a millimetre (Komolafe, 2018). The solar constant, which is 2 cal/cm²/min, is the amount of heat transferred from the Earth's surface to a unit area of 1 cm² in one minute. The transmission of solar energy takes the following forms: Shock Waves (Ultra Violet) <0.40 micron Ultraviolet (long-wave) > 0.76 micron Visible light makes up a negligible fraction of radiation, while heat accounts for the vast majority. 40 to 76 microns. A decrease in radiation intensity occurs as it passes through Earth's atmosphere because of: The atmospheric absorption of radiation is proportional to its wave length.

Ozone absorbs UV rays; infrared rays reach the earth through water vapour and carbon dioxide; and reflection Resulting from tiny droplets of water. On top of that, clouds significantly reduce the quantity of radiation that reaches Earth's surface by reflecting most of it back into space. When light strikes molecules that are the same size as or smaller than the light's wavelength, a phenomenon called radiation reflection and diffusion takes place. As a result of the scattering of shorter wavelengths (blue and violet light) by smaller molecules, the sky appears blue. The sky appears white when there are bigger dust particles in the atmosphere, which causes an increase in air turbidity and the scattering of long wave radiation (yellow and red) (Charles, 2018).

Consequently, as a result of the aforementioned losses, the Earth absorbed much less solar energy. The cloud tops reflect some of the sun's rays. Components in the air take in some of it. Atmospheric molecules deflect part of it, but some of it also returns as dispersed radiation. Air, ground, and things in the vicinity are heated because the majority of the radiation that reaches Earth's surface is either reflected or absorbed. The atmospheric absorption rate varied substantially between latitudes since it was only 15% of the total solar energy that reached Earth. The angle at which the sun's rays strike the Earth determines this (Bais et al., 2019).

Among the most important considerations in building design, particularly for ceiling design, is the quantity of rainfall. In regions prone to rainfall, gable roofs are the recommended architectural style for building ceilings. This helps to minimise water erosion, damage caused by rain, and the accumulation of water on roofs (Izomoh 2019). If this weren't the case, the problem of rainwater seeping into buildings would become much more severe. It is essential to know the rainfall rate in order to estimate the maximum likely rainfall when planning dams and other similar structures, since this information is crucial for determining spillway dimensions, etc. It seems that knowing the maximum urban flood related to return time is crucial for developing surface water disposal systems across cities during rainstorms.

Statement of the Problem

As a starting point, architects develop a notion, which is an underlying idea. In doing so, it directs and binds the project. The architect gives the building's design the overall direction and style. The fundamental ideas behind a building's design are known as architectural notions. By weaving together disparate elements, it unifies the building's architecture. According to the National Building Code (2016), architects are responsible for all aspects of a building's design and construction. A few of the long-standing demands placed on structures include, but are not limited to, keeping out intruders, avoiding the effects of gravity, and protecting occupants from extreme weather conditions (Encarta Dictionaries, 2018). With many factors to think about, it is the architect's job to create a structure that elegantly reflects the idea.

Poor design, planning, supervision, low-quality materials, absence of audits, improper supervision, design complexity, design concept, and other construction defects cause most government building projects to fail. The building's operational environment and the possible effects of climate change are not adequately considered throughout the design phase. Climate zones—which include factors like temperature, precipitation, wind speed and direction, humidity, and sunshine exposure—are not being adequately considered. Damage to the structure (such as cracks or collapses), problems with the electrical wiring or lighting, the plumbing, the drainage system, the HVAC system, insufficient insulation or soundproofing, and insufficient fire protection systems are among the most common defects caused by these factors. Termite or rat infestations, mildew, fungus, dry rot, or wood rot are all possible. Consequently, we embarked on a mission to quantify the impact of weather on secondary school enrollment in the Port Harcourt Local Government Area (LGA) in Rivers State.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of the study is to assess the Influence of Climatic Elements on the Utilization of Secondary School Buildings in Port Harcourt Local Government Area, Rivers State. Specifically, the study determined the following:

1. Influence of temperature on the Utilization of Secondary School Buildings in Port Harcourt Local Government Area, Rivers State.
2. Influence of wind on the Utilization of Secondary School Buildings in Port Harcourt Local Government Area, Rivers State.
3. Influence of solar radiation on the Utilization of Secondary School Buildings in Port Harcourt Local Government Area, Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study:

1. To what extent is the influence of temperature on the Utilization of Secondary School Buildings in Port Harcourt Local Government Area, Rivers State?
2. To what extent is the influence of wind on the Utilization of Secondary School Buildings in Port Harcourt Local Government Area, Rivers State?
3. To what extent is the influence of solar radiation on the Utilization of Secondary School Buildings in Port Harcourt Local Government Area, Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and will be tested at .05 level of significance:

H₀₁ There is no significant difference between the mean responses of builders and teachers on the influence of temperature on the Utilization of Secondary School Buildings in Port Harcourt Local Government Area, Rivers State.

H₀₂ There is no significant difference between the mean responses of builders and teachers on the influence of wind on the Utilization of Secondary School Buildings in Port Harcourt Local Government Area, Rivers State.

H₀₃ There is no significant difference between the mean responses of builders and teachers on the influence of solar radiation on the Utilization of Secondary School Buildings in Port Harcourt Local Government Area, Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

The researchers in this study used a survey methodology. The study's ability to collect data and information about how weather impacts secondary school building utilisation in Port Harcourt Local Government Area, Rivers State, supported the decision to utilise a survey research methodology. Port Harcourt, in the Rivers State Local Government Area, was the site of the research. With an average annual rainfall of around 2600 mm and a relative humidity of 67% during the rainiest months of December and January, this region has a subtropical climate. The south-west trade wind, a marine air mass that carries rain, is the dominant wind direction as it approaches Port Harcourt from the Atlantic Ocean. Port Harcourt's monthly rainfall is very regular, rising in the summer months of July and August before falling during the dry season of November through February. There is a regime of two maximum rainfall events in Port Harcourt. July and September get the most precipitation, while August is quite dry. July had the greatest monthly rainfall with 3496.1 mm, while September has the highest at 3578.4 mm. The small dry season, which occurs throughout July and August, is a respite for Port Harcourt.

All certified educators and builders in the Port Harcourt LGA made up the study's population. The Port Harcourt Local Government Area in Rivers State had a total of 180 respondents, 80 of whom were builders and 100 of whom were teachers (Field Survey 2023). The research used a census sampling approach. The statistical enumeration approach known as the census method involves studying the whole population. The population is manageable, which is the reason for this. The research used all 180 participants.

The research team in this study employed a structured questionnaire to gather information. As its name suggests, it is a survey measuring "Building Technology Climatic Elements" (BTCEQ). The instrument consists of Sections A through D. Very high extent (VHE), high extent (HE), uncertain (U), low extent (LE), and very low extent (VLEA) were the five-point response possibilities that formed the instrument. Each choice had a value of 5, 4, 3, 2, or 1. The tool has been face-validated by three professionals and has a reliability coefficient of 0.68. In order to evaluate the data collected from the participants and find answers to our research questions, we used a five-point rating system together with standard deviation and mean. To determine whether the null hypotheses were correct at the 0.05 level of significance, we used a t-test. If the value we calculated was more than or equal to the one in the table, we generally rejected the null hypothesis. But we accept the null hypothesis if the calculated value is less than the table value.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: To what extent is the influence of temperature on the Utilization of Secondary School Buildings in Port Harcourt Local Government Area, Rivers State?

Table 1: Mean and Standard deviation on the influence of temperature on the Utilization of Secondary School Buildings

	Temperature influence the following parts of Secondary School Buildings:	Builders			Teachers		
		X	SD	RMK	X	SD	RMK
1	Floor and Roof area	4.59	.62	HE	4.64	.49	HE
2	Eastern wall area	4.27	.76	HE	4.08	1.04	HE
3	Northern wall area	4.16	.71	HE	3.96	1.02	HE
4	Southern wall area	4.09	.96	HE	4.04	.89	HE
5	Western wall area	4.18	.92	HE	4.16	.94	HE
6	Door area	4.16	.89	HE	4.16	.75	HE
7	Window area	4.30	.98	HE	4.08	1.00	HE
8	Length of the wall	4.05	.94	HE	3.96	1.02	HE
9	Width of the wall	4.41	.73	HE	4.00	.96	HE
10	Height of the wall	4.00	.92	HE	3.92	1.15	HE
11	Emissivity of cement	4.00	.99	HE	4.44	.65	HE
12	Emissivity of concrete	4.57	.76	HE	4.28	1.02	HE
13	Emissivity of tiled floor	4.16	.78	HE	4.12	.83	HE
14	Absorptivity of cement	4.27	.85	HE	3.92	1.08	HE
15	Absorptivity of concrete	4.20	.85	HE	4.20	.91	HE

Table 4.1 shows that the mean range for Builders was 4.00-4.59 with a standard deviation of 0.62-0.99, and that the mean range for Teachers was 3.92-4.64 with a standard deviation of 0.049-1.08. The responders' similarity in proximity revealed their homogeneity. The majority of respondents in the Port Harcourt Local Government Area, Rivers State, said that temperature had a significant impact on the utilisation of secondary school buildings, according to the mean.

Research Question 2: To what extent is the influence of wind on the Utilization of Secondary School Buildings in Port Harcourt Local Government Area, Rivers State?

Table 2: Mean and Standard deviation on the influence of wind on the Utilization of Secondary School Buildings

S/N	Wind influence the following parts of Secondary School Buildings:	Builders			Teachers		
		X	SD	RMK	X	SD	RMK
16	Floor and Roof area	4.36	.89	HE	4.00	1.08	HE
17	Eastern wall area	3.93	1.00	HE	4.24	.97	HE
18	Northern wall area	4.14	1.15	HE	4.12	1.05	HE
19	Southern wall area	4.16	1.14	HE	3.92	1.04	HE
20	Western wall area	4.14	.98	HE	4.32	.69	HE
21	Door area	3.98	.93	HE	4.00	.96	HE
22	Window area	4.09	.94	HE	4.20	.91	HE
23	Length of the wall	4.11	.92	HE	4.36	.81	HE
24	Width of the wall	4.00	.96	HE	4.12	.60	HE
25	Height of the wall	3.89	1.15	HE	4.04	1.24	HE
26	Emissivity of cement	3.95	1.29	HE	4.48	.71	HE
27	Emissivity of concrete	4.07	.87	HE	4.20	.76	HE
28	Emissivity of tiled floor	3.77	1.27	HE	4.12	.93	HE
29	Absorptivity of cement	3.91	.96	HE	3.88	1.13	HE
30	Absorptivity of concrete	4.02	1.05	HE	4.08	.76	HE

Table 2 shows that average scores for construction workers were between 3.75 and 4.36, with a standard deviation of 0.85 to 1.29, and that scores for educators were between 3.72-4.48, with a standard variation of 0.60 to 1.24. The close closeness of the replies proved how similar they were. The majority of respondents in the Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State believe that wind has a major effect on the location and usage of secondary schools in the area. As a third question, how does the amount of sunlight reaching secondary school buildings in Rivers State's Port Harcourt LGA affect their utilisation?

Research Question 3: To what extent is the influence of solar radiation on the Utilization of Secondary School Buildings in Port Harcourt Local Government Area, Rivers State?

Table 3: Mean and Standard deviation on the influence of solar radiation on the Utilization of Secondary School Buildings

S/N	Solar radiation influences the following parts of Secondary School Buildings:	Builders			Teachers		
		X	SD	RMK	X	SD	RMK
54	Floor and Roof area	3.70	1.17	HE	4.16	1.03	HE
55	Eastern wall area	3.75	1.14	HE	3.84	.94	HE
56	Northern wall area	4.11	.97	HE	4.2	.764	HE
57	Southern wall area	3.82	.87	HE	3.92	.95	HE
58	Western wall area	4.07	.97	HE	4.12	1.09	HE
59	Door area	4.16	1.03	HE	4.00	1.23	HE
60	Window area	4.14	.85	HE	4.08	.86	HE
61	Length of the wall	3.75	1.04	HE	3.68	1.11	HE
62	Width of the wall	4.20	.98	HE	4.12	.93	HE
63	Height of the wall	3.95	.94	HE	4.00	1.00	HE
64	Emissivity of cement	4.23	.94	HE	3.92	1.12	HE
65	Emissivity of concrete	4.43	.85	HE	3.92	1.08	HE

66	Emissivity of tiled floor	3.95	.86	HE	3.92	1.19	HE
67	Absorptivity of cement	4.16	1.06	HE	4.20	.82	HE
68	Absorptivity of concrete	4.39	.69	HE	4.24	1.05	HE

Table 3 shows that the mean range for Builders was 3.70-4.43 with a standard deviation of 0.69-1.17, and that the mean range for Teachers was 3.68-4.24 with a standard deviation of 0.82-1.23. The proximity demonstrated the responses' similarity. The respondents in Port Harcourt Local Government Area, Rivers State, said that solar radiation significantly affects the use of secondary school buildings.

Hypotheses

H₀₁ There is no significant difference between the mean responses of builders and teachers on the influence of temperature on the Utilization of Secondary School Buildings in Port Harcourt Local Government Area, Rivers State.

Table 4: t-Test Analysis on the influence of temperature on the Utilization of Secondary School Buildings

Groups	Mean	SD	N	Df	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
Builders	4.19	0.89	15				
				128	1.41	1.96	Accepted
Teachers	4.10	0.93	115				

A t-cal of 1.41 is less than a t-crit of 1.96, as seen in Table 4. Finding no statistically significant difference in the two groups' average replies to the topic of how temperature impacts the utilisation of secondary school buildings in the Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State, the findings demonstrated that the hypothesis was valid.

H₀₂ There is no significant difference between the mean responses of builders and teachers on the influence of wind on the Utilization of Secondary School Buildings in Port Harcourt Local Government Area, Rivers State.

Table 5: t-Test Analysis on the influence of wind on the Utilization of Secondary School Buildings

Groups	Mean	SD	N	Df	t-cal	t-cri	Decision
Builders	3.94	1.03	15				
				128	0.25	1.96	Accepted
Teachers	4.05	0.90	115				

A t-cal of 0.25 is lower than a t-crit of 1.96, as seen in Table 5. Finding no statistically significant difference between the two groups' average replies to the topic of how wind influences the utilisation of secondary school buildings in the Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State, the findings demonstrated that the hypothesis was valid.

H₀₃ There is no significant difference between the mean responses of builders and teachers on the influence of solar radiation on the Utilization of Secondary School Buildings in Port Harcourt Local Government Area, Rivers State.

Table 6: t-Test Analysis on the influence of solar radiation on the Utilization of Secondary School Buildings

Groups	Mean	SD	N	Df	t-cal	t-cri	Decision
Builders	4.07	0.94	15				
				128	-0.44	1.96	Accepted
Teachers	3.99	1.03	115				

A t-cal of -0.44 is lower than a t-crit of 1.96, as seen in Table 6. The findings supported the hypothesis, and in the Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State, there was no statistically significant difference in the ratings given by teachers and builders about the influence of solar radiation on the utilisation of secondary school buildings.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Findings showed that residents of the Port Harcourt LGA in Rivers State agreed that temperature significantly affected the use of secondary school facilities. There was no statistically significant difference between the averages of the responses provided by teachers and builders in the Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State regarding the influence of temperature on the usage of secondary school facilities. This finding supports the previously stated hypothesis. Koch (2017) stated that when designing reinforced concrete elements, it is important to take into account the change in temperature that occurs between the concrete's peak temperature during early hydration (usually within the first week after placement) and the minimum temperature that the element will experience under service conditions. This finding is consistent with the study's findings. Concrete has little stress due to the early increase in hydration temperature. During the temperature increase phase and while concrete is young, its elastic modulus is low, and creep readily alleviates compressive stresses caused by constrained expansion. As concrete cools, it ages and becomes less pliable due to the restricted thermal contraction and the resulting tensile stresses (Kwok, 2018). At the halfway and one-third locations along a bay, they may be large enough to induce cracking. Assuming there is no initial stress allows for a more realistic and conservative interpretation to emerge. A temperature shift of around 10 °C is enough to cause cracking in the worst case scenario of a completely constrained element. Hence, fracture promotion does not need substantial temperature spikes, which may cause long-term strength losses. But without any kind of constraint, the concrete may shrink without breaking.

A large majority of people surveyed in the Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State agreed that wind significantly affected the occupancy rates of secondary school buildings, according to the study's findings. Teachers and building owners in Rivers State's Port Harcourt Local Government Area were in agreement that wind would have a negative effect on secondary school building usage, lending credence to the theory.

The results of the research corroborate those of Malaragno (2012), who argued that variations in temperature impact the water content, relative humidity, and creep and shrinkage of concrete at an early age. Predicted and actual responses to temperature changes may diverge significantly if the creep and shrinkage responses are disregarded and full histories of concrete water content, temperature, and loads are not taken into account. When it comes to concrete, the majority of studies have focused on how temperature affects shrinkage and creep. Very little is known about how a whole building reacts to changes in temperature throughout the year.

Researchers in Rivers State found that secondary school buildings in the Port Harcourt Local Government Area were much less used when exposed to solar radiation. When asked how solar radiation impacts the utilisation of secondary school buildings in the Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State, there was no statistically significant difference between the means of the construction workers' and educators' comments. These results provide credence to the theory that was advanced before. The findings of this research are in agreement with those of Liman and Abadie (2019), who described how temperature fluctuations may significantly affect the deflections that reinforced concrete structures undergo.

The formation of a temperature gradient between two surfaces of an unconstrained flexural member causes deflections in that member. Tensile loads applied to the member might cause cracking and a decrease in flexural stiffness in situations when temperature-related deformations are limited. It is common practice to ignore the impact of temperature on deflection when designing structures as it seldom influences the eventual limit state. Since the degree of cracking depends on the thermal load,

Mba et al. (2021) notes that in order to determine the ultimate strain distribution in fractured sections, an iterative approach is required. Regarding design, though, he recommends using the uncracked section to determine unrestrained thermal curvature and the moment of inertia linked to the expected distribution of cracks at service loads to determine thermal continuity moments and secondary thermal stresses.

Conclusion

A quantitative method formed the basis of this investigation. The study's overarching goal was to help construction management professionals better understand how climate change would affect their work throughout a project's lifespan. In order to lessen the impact of climate change on secondary school buildings in Port Harcourt, this study set out to examine the history of climate change in the area under investigation, determine which stages of a construction project are most impacted by climate change factors, and provide a reasonable strategy to help professionals in the field compare their work to that of other stages.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, following recommendations were made:

1. It is essential that architects and owners prioritise the orientation of school buildings in order to reduce dangers and maximise passive benefits of wind and sun.
2. The ministry of education should provide minimum standards for educational facilities to adhere to during construction to accommodate climatic factors
3. The use of sustainable building practices, construction methods and materials for the construction of secondary school buildings and educational facilities should be enshrined in the requirement for statutory approvals from regulatory bodies.

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